

Tracking Reaction Pathways by a Modular Flow Reactor Coupled to Electrospray Ionization Mass Spectrometry

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Reaction monitoring by electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) is a popular method for investigation of reaction mechanisms. Here, we present a new approach based on a coupling between a modular capillary flow reactor and ESI-MS. The flow reactor allows a sequential adding of the reactants. We demonstrate the approach for oxidation of Ph₂S by ArIO catalyzed by [(TPA)Fe^{IV}O(X)]^{2+/+} (ArIO = 2-(^tBuSO₂)C₆H₄IO, TPA = tris(2-pyridylmethyl)amine, TfO⁻ = triflate). In steps, we could follow the formation of the reactive iron(IV)oxo complexes, then

the oxygen transfer reaction from the iron(IV)oxo to the sulfide, and finally the reoxidation of the iron complexes. The flow reactor also allows kinetic experiments by changing relative concentrations of the reactants. We could analyze in detail the formation of various [(TPA)Fe^{IV}O(X)]^{2+/+} complexes (X = MeCN, ArI, ArIO, TfO⁻) and compare their relative reactivity with Ph₂S. The [(TPA)Fe^{IV}O(MeCN)]²⁺ complex is the most reactive complex for the oxygen atom transfer reaction whilst [(TPA)Fe^{IV}O(ArIO)]²⁺ prevails in solution under catalytic conditions.

1. Introduction

Introduction of electrospray ionization (ESI) opened a field of investigation of species formed and present in solution by mass spectrometry (MS).^[1] One of the opened directions is reaction monitoring and applications towards the investigation of reaction mechanisms.^[2–6] The advantage of mass spectrometry consists in high sensitivity and thus possibility of detecting minor species from solution.^[7] Hence, mass spectrometric investigation of reaction mechanisms is particularly advantageous for catalytic reactions in which short lived, highly reactive and thus low abundant reaction intermediates play a role.

Direct reaction monitoring with ESI-MS can provide valuable data on reaction intermediates and their kinetics during the reaction.^[8] However, the data are burdened by the uncertainty of the ionization efficiency and artifacts of electrospray ionization. Moreover, the monitoring requires recording ESI-MS spectra during the whole reaction time, which can be time-consuming. In this paper, we present an alternative approach – ESI-MS monitoring of reactions in modular flow reactors.^[9,10] Modular flow reactors bring three major advantages: 1) rapid reaction screening; 2) access to reaction kinetics in solution using ESI-MS monitoring; and 3) the possibility to assess the ESI-MS artifacts.

Herein, we demonstrate the potential of the flow reactor – ESI-MS coupling for research of catalytic reactions. Namely, we investigate the oxygen transfer reaction (OAT) from an iodosoarene oxidant to a sulfide proceeding via reactive iron(IV)oxo

intermediates (Figure 1a, TPA = tris(2-pyridylmethyl)amine, X = solvent molecule or other available ligands present in solution).^[11,12] These types of complexes are investigated as biomimetic models of non-heme iron-oxo enzymatic reaction centers.^[13–17]

2. Results and Discussion

In the investigation of a reaction such as the one shown in Figure 1a, one can ask several mechanistic questions. For example, what are the reactive species and what is their speciation in solution (i.e., what is the identity of the iron(IV) oxo intermediate)? How is this reactive intermediate formed (i.e., the red arrow in Figure 1a)? How does this reactive intermediate react with a substrate (i.e., the blue arrow in

Figure 1. a) Oxygen transfer reaction proceeding via reactive iron(IV)oxo intermediates. b) Modular flow reactor. The reactor is built from silica capillaries and the flow is regulated by nitrogen overpressure in the vials (not shown here, see Figure 8 for details). The reaction time is a combination of the flow rate and the length of the capillaries. The vials can be sequentially filled with reactants to test one reaction step after the other.

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Figure 1a)? And finally, is the reaction catalytic? We found that all these questions can be answered by testing the reactivity in the flow reactor shown in Figure 1b.

We started to monitor the reaction mixture by the subsequent addition of reactants to the flow reactor shown in Figure 1b (the setup was cooled to -40°C). The addition of a solution of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{TfO})_2]$ in acetonitrile (1 mM) to vial A (the remaining vials are filled with only acetonitrile) led to the detection of both $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ (m/z 193.5) and $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TfO})]^{+}$ (m/z 495) (Figure 2a). When vial B is filled with 1.4 mM solution of the oxidant ArIO (ArIO = $2\text{-}(\text{tBuSO}_2)\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{IO}$, see Figure 1), we observed a complete transformation of the iron complexes to iron(IV)oxo species $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{MeCN}$ (m/z 201.5), ArI (m/z 343), ArIO (m/z 351), TfO^- (m/z 511), Figure 2b).^[18] These results highlight the red part of the cycle in Figure 1a and indicate the speciation of the reactive iron(IV)oxo complexes.

Next, we tested the blue part of the cycle in Figure 1a. We filled vial C with a 4 mM solution of Ph_2S and monitored the formation of species involved in the OAT reaction. We have detected almost quantitative reduction of the iron(IV) complexes to the respective iron(II) complexes. We have also detected iron(II) complexes bearing the sulfoxide product as a ligand (Figure 2c).

Finally, to close the cycle, we tested the re-oxidation of the iron(II) complexes formed by OAT by another portion of the ArIO oxidant. To this end, we added a 1.4 mM solution of an isotopically labeled oxidant (ArI^{18}O) to vial D. The corresponding spectrum in Figure 2d clearly shows the reoxidation of iron(II)

complexes to the ^{18}O -labeled iron(IV)oxo species alongside with further transformation of diphenylsulfide to the labeled sulfoxide (Ph_2S was used in excess).

These sequential experiments with the flow reactor allowed us to track the catalytic cycle using mass spectrometric detection of reactive species. However, further experiments are necessary to assure that ESI-MS indeed detects species relevant for the solution chemistry. For example, we detected various speciation of iron(IV)oxo complex $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ with $\text{X} = \text{MeCN}$, ArI, ArIO and TfO^- but the question remains whether all these species are relevant for solution chemistry. Another relevant question concerns the mechanism of the formation of these reactive complexes. And in order to answer these questions, one needs to study kinetics of the formation of these ions.

2.1. Investigation of Kinetics with Flow Reactor/ESI-MS

The way to test whether the ESI-MS spectra reflect the chemical processes in solution is to couple the spectra with reaction kinetics in solution. The reaction rate can be monitored either by changing the reaction time or by changing concentrations of the reactants. Changing the reaction time in the flow reactor can be achieved by changing the capillary length and/or the flow rate of the reaction mixture (see Figure 1b). Herein we varied both the capillary length and the solution flow. Varying only the length while keeping the flow constant can be achieved only by simultaneous changing of the overpressure in the vials (the longer the capillary, the larger the pressure must be to achieve the same flow rate). This is difficult to achieve, therefore we modified the capillary length while using a constant overpressure and then changed the overpressure while using a constant capillary length. To investigate the role of reactant concentrations we simply prepared vials with a varying concentration and exchanged them during the experiments.

2.2. Oxidation of Iron(II) Complexes by ArIO

To study the formation of iron(IV)oxo complexes, we used a flow setup with only two vials. The first vial was filled with 1 mM solution of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TfO})_2]$ in acetonitrile and the second vial was filled with acetonitrile solutions of ArIO in varying concentrations (Figure 3). By varying the capillary length and the flow we reached reaction times of 4, 7, 35, 45, and 70 s. The reaction time was experimentally determined by measuring the time from the start of the experiment to the appearance of signals belonging to the iron complexes (see Experimental Details and Figure 9).

We firstly evaluated the overall kinetic profile of the oxidation of iron(II) complexes (Figures 3a–3e). Therefore, we summed the ion abundances of all the detected iron(II) complexes ($[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$) and iron(IV)oxo complexes ($[(\text{TPA})\text{FeO}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$). In addition, we detected iron(III) complexes ($[(\text{TPA})_2\text{Fe}_2(\text{O})(\text{TfO})]^{3+}$) resulting from reaction between the iron(II) and iron(IV) complexes.

Figure 2. ESI-MS spectra of reaction mixtures resulting from sequential mixing of solutions in vials A–D (Scheme 1); the flow was constant, temperature was -40°C . The concentrations of the acetonitrile solutions in the vials were: A: $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{TfO})_2]$ (1 mM), B: ArIO (1.4 mM), C: Ph_2S (4 mM), D: ArI^{18}O (1.4 mM). If the given reactant was not used in an experiment, the vial was filled with only acetonitrile.

Figure 3. Results of ESI-MS monitoring of the oxidation reaction in a flow reactor ($T = 25^\circ\text{C}$). Reaction was initiated by mixing solution A (1 mM $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{TfO})_2]$ in acetonitrile) and solution B (a variable concentration of ArIO in acetonitrile – see the x-axis). a–e) Relative abundance of ESI-MS detected iron(II), iron(IV)oxo, and binuclear iron(III) $[(\text{TPA})_2\text{Fe}_2(\text{O})(\text{TfO})]^{3+}$ complexes as a function of the reaction time in a flow reactor. f–j) Branching ratios between ESI-MS detected $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ (X is color-coded indicated in the figure) as a function of the reaction time in the flow reactor.

The dependence of the transformation of iron(II) to iron(IV) oxo complexes on the concentration of the ArIO oxidant is within the experimental error identical for all reaction times. This result suggests that the oxidation reaction is fast and already reached an equilibrium at the shortest reaction times tested (4 and 7 s). The quantitative transformation of iron(II) to iron(IV)oxo complexes is achieved using 1.4–1.6 equivalents of ArIO.^[19] This is in agreement with the fact that some of the iron(IV)oxo complexes are formulated as $[(\text{TPA})\text{FeO}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ and thus not all ArIO is available for the oxidation reaction.^[13]

Interestingly, with increasing reaction time, we observed an increased formation of the undesired iron(III) complexes (Figures 3a–3e and Figures S3a–S3e in the Supporting Information). Formation of the dimeric iron(III) complex is explained by the

reaction between iron(IV)oxo and iron(II) complexes (Reaction 1). The relative yield of iron(III) complexes positively correlates with the reaction time in the flow reactor (yellow in Figures 3a–3e). This indicates that the dimerization is slower than the oxidation reaction. Accordingly, this reaction is completely suppressed once the concentration of the ArIO oxidant is sufficient to rapidly oxidize all iron(II) complexes to iron(IV)oxo. Besides the kinetic information, these results clearly show that we monitor reactivity in solution and not gas-phase artifacts. We note that we cannot exclude possible reactions in droplets during electrospray ionization.^[20,21] Droplet environment can accelerate the reactions leading to an apparent higher conversion. However, this should not change the qualitative information about the reaction (see also the Experimental Section). In our case, the experimental conditions favoring the droplet reaction acceleration result in a higher yield of the iron(III) clusters (cf. Figure 7). However, throughout this work, we used conditions suppressing the possible droplet reactions. The acceleration was negligible as evidenced by the almost absent signal of iron(III) clusters for short reaction times in the flow.

Next, we analyzed the branching ratios between the detected iron(IV)oxo complexes in dependence of the reaction time and the concentration of the oxidant (Figures 3f–3j). It is important to note that the ion transfer during electrospray ionization can be different for different complexes and thus the relative concentrations might be in reality quite different from the detected relative ion intensities.^[3,22] Therefore, we analyze only the trends. Furthermore, at large concentrations of ArIO, we observed the oxidation of ArIO to ArIO_2 and the formation of the corresponding $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO}_2)]^{2+}$ complex. For the sake of simplicity, we have summed the abundances of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ and $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO}_2)]^{2+}$ in further evaluation. For the original dataset see Figure S3.

At first glance, the concentration dependence of the branching ratios is similar for different reaction times. The general trends are (i) the relative abundance of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ peaks at small conversions of Fe^{II} to Fe^{IV} and decreases with further conversion and with increasing concentration of ArIO; (ii) the relative abundances of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArI})]^{2+}$ and $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{TfO})]^{+}$ increase with increasing conversion of Fe^{II} to Fe^{IV} (leading to the formation of ArI as a by-product) and then slightly decrease; (iii) the relative abundance of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ peaks at the smallest concentrations of ArIO, then decreases at the expense of the formation of the other iron(IV)oxo complexes, but finally again rises after the complete conversion of Fe^{II} to Fe^{IV} .

The comparison of different reaction times reveals one important fact: the maximum of the relative abundance of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ shifts with increasing reaction time to higher concentrations of ArIO. This is most likely correlated with the depletion of its concentration by Reaction 1. Reaction 1 requires decoordination of ligand X from $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ (unless $\text{X} = \text{TfO}^-$). The theoretical binding energies (BDE) of the X ligands are $BDE(\text{CH}_3\text{CN}) = 8.9 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $BDE(\text{ArI}) = 10.4 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $BDE(\text{TfO}^-) = 12.6 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $BDE(\text{ArIO}) = 25.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.^[13] Hence, the binding energy of ArIO is much larger than the binding energy of acetonitrile as well as triflate.

Thus, the ArIO ligand “protects” the iron(IV)oxo complex against Reaction 1. This explains why $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ has a relatively large abundance at low concentrations of ArIO, which otherwise would be strongly counterintuitive. Reaction 1 also explains the low relative abundance of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{TfO})]^{+}$ at the low ArIO concentrations: the concentration of free TfO^{-} decreases at the cost of $[(\text{TPA})_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}(\text{TfO})]^{3+}$ formation.

In summary, these results suggest that we see formation of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+}$ with $\text{X} = \text{MeCN}$, ArI, ArIO and TfO^{-} in quasi-equilibrium. At low oxidation conversions of iron(II) complexes, we observe depletion of iron(IV)oxo complexes with $\text{X} = \text{MeCN}$ and TfO^{-} by Reaction 1. The complexes $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ bearing the strongly bound ligand ArIO are protected against Reaction 1, therefore they prevail at the low conversion conditions although the concentration of ArIO is small.

2.3. Oxygen Transfer Reaction from Iron(IV)oxo to Ph_2S

In the next step, we have investigated the kinetics of the oxygen atom transfer between the iron(IV)oxo complexes and diphenylsulfide. We have varied the reaction time by the flow rate and also by the length of the capillary (see Supporting Information for details). To simplify the conditions, we have used a flow reactor with just one mixing point. The first vial contained a mixture of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TfO})_2]$ (1 mM) and Ph_2S (variable concentration, see Figure 4) in acetonitrile. The second vial contained a 1.2 mM solution of the oxidant ArIO in acetonitrile. After the mixing, the oxidation of the iron complex and the subsequent oxygen atom transfer to Ph_2S could proceed simultaneously (both parts of the catalytic cycle in Figure 1a). We have investigated the effect of the changing concentration of Ph_2S on the overall kinetics of the reaction (Figure 4).

For evaluation of the kinetics, we have extracted the relative intensities of the detected signals of the iron(IV)oxo reactants (Figures 4a–4e) and the iron(II) products (Figures 4f–4j). Several iron(II) complexes were coordinated to the $\text{Ph}_2\text{S}=\text{O}$ product as a ligand (e.g., the signals shown in light blue in Figure 4). The spectra contain more signals: the full list of the complexes and all the data are in the Supporting Information (Figure S4).

We will start with the analysis of the kinetic data for the detected iron(II) complexes (the left column in Figure 4). The data show a positive correlation of the iron(II) complexes' yields and the concentration of the Ph_2S substrate. The reaction time has a minor effect. The only obvious effect is visible for the signal of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{MeCN})]^{+}$ (the orange lines in the left column of Figure 4). At short reaction times (13 and 16 s), not all iron(II) complexes got transformed into iron(IV)oxo complexes; therefore, we detected non-zero intensity of iron(II) complexes also for the zero and low concentrations of Ph_2S . For longer reaction times, the transformation of the initial iron(II) complexes to the reactive iron(IV)oxo complexes was completed, therefore we see the (re)formation of iron(II) complexes only with increasing concentration of Ph_2S .

The incomplete transformation of iron(II) complexes to iron(IV)oxo complexes at short reaction times is connected with a somewhat smaller rate of the $\text{Ph}_2\text{S}=\text{O}$ formation at low

Figure 4. Results of ESI-MS monitoring of a reaction in a flow reactor ($T = 25^\circ\text{C}$). Reaction was initiated by mixing solution A (1 mM $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{TfO})_2]$ and variable concentration of Ph_2S – see the x-axis - in acetonitrile) and solution B (1.2 mM ArIO in acetonitrile). a–e) Relative normalized abundances of the ESI-MS detected $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ complexes as a function of the reaction time in the flow reactor. f–j) Relative abundance of selected $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ complexes as a function of the reaction time in the flow reactor. X is always color-coded and indicated in the figure.

concentrations of Ph_2S (see the slower rise of the light blue curves at the onset for short reaction times). This small difference points to the fact that the oxygen transfer between iron(IV)oxo complexes and Ph_2S is a fast reaction with kinetics comparable to the initial iron oxidation.

Next to the formation of the sulfoxide product, we can also observe overoxidation to the sulfone (Ph_2SO_2 , dark blue lines in Figure 4, left panel). The overoxidation is more pronounced for longer reaction times and small concentrations of the sulfide substrate. Once the Ph_2S substrate is in excess, the second oxygen atom transfer reaction to one substrate molecule is suppressed (see Figure S5 for GC-MS analysis of products).

Secondly, we compared the kinetics associated with the detected iron(IV)oxo complexes (the right column in Figure 4). For an easier comparison, we have normalized the relative intensities to one. The decays of the $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ signal for $\text{X} = \text{MeCN}$, TfO^{-} and ArI are very similar. On the contrary, the decay of $[(\text{TPA})$

$\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})^{2+}$ (cyan curve in the right column of Figure 4) is clearly slower. The data suggest that the $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ complex reacts slower in the oxygen transfer reaction than the other detected complexes. However, the data reflect not only the OAT reaction, but also the equilibrium reaction among the complexes. In addition, at shorter reaction times, the kinetics are further complicated by the not completed initial iron(II) oxidation. Hence, the data are not conclusive.

In order to compare the reactivities of the iron(IV)oxo complexes under well-defined conditions, we have tested their reactivity in the gas phase.^[23–25] Each complex was mass-selected and reacted with a molecule of Me_2S . We have used Me_2S instead of Ph_2S because of the better volatility of the former. The gas-phase reaction between $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ and Me_2S leads to the formation of a complex followed by the elimination of the $\text{Me}_2\text{S}=\text{O}$ product (Reaction 2) or by the elimination of the neutral ligand X (Reaction 3). The complex $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ can either react according to Reactions 2 and 3, or it can provide double oxygen atom transfer leading to the $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{ArI})]^{2+}$ product (Figure 5b). The second oxygen atom transfer reaction is favored because the possible product of the first oxygen atom transfer, $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$, can rearrange to a stronger oxidant than the initial $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ complex, i.e., to $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArI})]^{2+}$. Hence, one complex of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ can oxidize two molecules of Me_2S in the gas phase. Alternatively, both oxygen atom transfers could occur to only one molecule of Me_2S . Accordingly, next to the dominant $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{Me}_2\text{S}=\text{O})]^{2+}$ signal we detected also a trace signal of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_2)]^{2+}$.

Figure 5. Gas-phase reactivity of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$, X = ArIO, TfO⁻, ArI, and MeCN with Me_2S at $E_{\text{coll}} = 0$ eV. a) Relative abundance of the parent ions as a function of the Me_2S pressure. b) Reaction of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ with Me_2S ($P = 0.15$ mTorr). c) Reaction of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ with Me_2S ($P = 0.15$ mTorr).

The complex $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ reacts only via Reaction 3, because the product $\text{Me}_2\text{S}=\text{O}$ has a much larger binding energy than MeCN. The overall conversion of the parent ions as a function of the Me_2S pressure shows that the $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ complex reacts fastest, whereas the $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ reacts slowest (Figure 5a). The data are in agreement with the estimate that we obtained from the solution experiments (Figure 4).

This result is in striking contrast with the previously shown hydrogen-atom transfer (HAT) reactivity of these complexes.^[13] The $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{ArIO})]^{2+}$ complex reacts fastest in HAT, but slowest in OAT and the $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ complex reacts slowest in HAT, but fastest in OAT. This suggests that the *cis*-ligand might have a considerable effect on the selectivity of the HAT vs. OAT reactions.

Scheme 1 summarizes the kinetic experiments shown in Figures 3 and 4. The iron(II) complexes can be in a fast reaction oxidized by ArIO to the iron(IV)oxo complexes. The competing degradation of the catalytic iron complexes to unreactive iron(III) dimers is slow and can be suppressed by using excess of ArIO. The excess of ArIO has two benefits: (i) it accelerates the oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(IV) and (ii) it acts as a strongly bound ligand that inhibits the degradation reaction of the generated Fe(IV) complex. The iron(IV)oxo complexes react in the oxygen atom transfer reaction with Ph_2S to form sulfoxides. If the concentration of Ph_2S is small with respect to the reactive iron(IV)oxo complexes, then the reaction can continue to form sulfones. The $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ complex with the weakest bound *cis*-ligand provides the fastest OAT reaction, whereas the complex with the strongest bound ligand ArIO reacts slowest. Hence, the catalytic reaction should be done with the excess of ArIO to assure the efficient formation of the reactive iron(IV)oxo species, but too much excess of ArIO could slow down the second part of the catalytic cycle concerning the oxygen atom transfer to the organic substrate.

3. Conclusion

The paper shows that the coupling of a flow reactor with electrospray ionization mass spectrometry can provide a de-

Scheme 1. Overview of the reactions detected by ESI-MS.

tailed insight into a reactive mixture. The sequential addition of reactants into a flow reactor allows a subsequent evaluation of the reaction steps. We have shown here that it can be used to monitor a catalytic cycle. For the selected oxygen transfer reaction, the results show the initial formation of the reactive hypervalent iron(IV)oxo species from the iron(II) precursor and an oxidant (ArIO). The subsequent addition of a substrate (Ph_2S) shows that all iron(IV)oxo complexes transfer the oxygen atom to the substrate. Finally, the addition of another portion of the oxidant shows that the reduced iron complexes can be again reoxidized to the reactive iron(IV)oxo species.

We further demonstrated that the flow reactor could be used to qualitatively monitor reaction kinetics in solution. To this end, we varied concentrations of the reactants in the flow reactor. In order to prove that the detected changes are associated with the reactions in solution (rather than with the changing ESI-MS conditions), we have also varied reaction time by changing the length and the flow of the capillary reactor. The results provided an insight into the formation of the iron(IV)oxo complexes and also into the oxygen atom transfer reactivity (Scheme 1).

4. Outlook

Monitoring of the reaction progression using a flow setup can be exploited not only for elucidating reaction mechanisms, but also for reaction optimizations or even the discovery of novel chemical transformations. For such a global approach, the screening of the reaction conditions must be swift, computer-controlled and must result in reproducible electro-spraying conditions and thus comparable mass spectra. To this end, we are developing a computer-controlled flow reactor, where the concentrations of the reactants and the reaction times of each reaction step can be smoothly altered while the flow rate into the mass spectrometer is kept constant (see the Supporting Information for details). For the reaction investigated in this paper, this approach provided a matrix of data dependent on the concentration of the oxidant (ArIO), on the concentration of the substrate (Ph_2S), on the reaction time for the oxidation of the catalyst and on the reaction time for the oxygen atom transfer to Ph_2S . Figure 6 shows the results for both reaction times set to 15 s. We will not discuss the data, because they are consistent with the interpretation of the data above. The figure should illustrate the potential of the flow

Figure 6. Integrated relative ion intensities normalized to the total ion current of (i) left column: all detected $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ and $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$; (ii) middle column: $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{MeCN}, \text{TfO}^-, \text{ArI}$, and Ph_2SO – the last channel includes also complexes with Ph_2SO_2 , $2 \times \text{Ph}_2\text{SO}$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{SO} + \text{ArI}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{SO}_2 + \text{ArI}$) and (iii) right column: $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{X})]^{2+/+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{MeCN}, \text{TfO}^-, \text{ArI}$, and ArIO – the last channel includes also complexes with ArIO and $\text{ArIO}_2 + \text{TfO}^-$). Reaction was performed with concentration of 1 mM for $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{TfO})_2]$, variable concentration of Ph_2S (vertical) and variable concentrations of ArIO (horizontal). The reaction temperature was 25 °C and both reaction times were 15 s (see the scheme on top). For more information, see the Supporting Information.

reactor – ESI-MS approach to provide data for computer-aided exploration and design of new reactions.

Experimental Section

Chemical Synthesis. The chemicals 2-(*tert*-butylsulfonyl)iodosylbenzene (2-(*tert*-BuSO₂)C₆H₄IO₂) and [(TPA)Fe(OTf)₂] were prepared according to published procedures.^[26]

Electrospray Mass Spectrometry Experiments. The experiments were performed with a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (TSQ Classic) equipped with an electrospray ionization source.^[27] The complexes were transferred from the solution to the gas phase at soft ionization conditions and mass-analyzed by the first quadrupole (the octupole and the second quadrupole were in the total transmission mode). The ions are detected by a conversion dynode and electron multiplier. Electrospray conditions typically were: 4 kV spray voltage, 200 °C capillary temperature, 0 V capillary voltage, 40 V tube lens voltage, 40 psi of N₂ sheath gas. The iron(IV)oxo complexes partially rearrange to iron(II) complexes with self-oxidized ligand during the ion transfer, if the capillary temperature is set to 200 °C.^[13] The rearrangement is a gas-phase artefact and the detected signals still report on the iron(IV)oxo complexes transferred from the solution. This rearrangement can be suppressed by setting the capillary temperature to 50 °C. Therefore, the gas-phase reactivity studies were made at the decreased capillary temperature. The reaction monitoring was performed at 200 °C, because the ion signal is substantially higher under these conditions and the possible gas-phase rearrangement of the ions does not affect the monitoring results.

The process of electrospray ionization can lead to an acceleration of the reactions in droplets.^[20] Such a process may result in the ESI-MS detection of an apparent larger conversion than would correspond to the real conversion in solution. This effect is dependent of the life time and the size of the droplets during the electrospray. The longer the life time and the smaller the size of the droplets, the larger the possible reaction acceleration. We have an in-line configuration of the electrospray ionization capillary and the transfer capillary entrance to the mass spectrometry with a small distance (~1 cm) which should minimize the possibility of the reaction acceleration during the spray.^[28] In addition, we use a large sheath gas flow (40 psi) to accelerate the droplet desolvation. We have tested the effect of the droplet flight distance and the effect of the sheath gas flow on the reactivity outcome (Figure 7). We did not detect any significant effect of the maximum available change of the droplet flight-distance in our setup (1 cm vs. 7 cm) on the reactivity outcome. We did detect the effect of the sheath gas flow. With changing of the nitrogen flow, the degradation of the reactive complexes to iron(III) clusters changed from about 10% (40 psi N₂) to about 30% (10 psi N₂) of the overall intensity. Hence, this effect must be kept in mind and checked during all reaction monitoring using ESI-MS. We also checked all reported trends with the new automated setup LabM8 that controls the constant spray flow to the ESI source. The results are analogous to the results reported here (see Figure S7). We note that the reaction acceleration in droplets could be advantageous for slow reactions, because the flow chemistry and the concentration dependent experiments could still provide information on the reactivity trends.

Gas-Phase Reactivity Experiments. Ions were mass-selected by the first quadrupole and collided with Me₂S at variable pressures in the collision cell. The products of the gas-phase collisions were mass-analyzed by the second quadrupole and detected by a dynode/multiplier system. The manifold temperature of the TSQ instrument was kept constant at 70 °C. The pressure in the collision cell was

Figure 7. The effect of the electrospray conditions on the reaction conversion in the flow-ESI-MS setup. The spectra were obtained using two different spray voltages (4 kV and 7 kV, respectively), two different nitrogen sheath gas flows (set by 10 psi and 40 psi N₂ pressure, respectively), and two different spraying distances (1 cm and 7 cm, respectively). The bottom bar graphs show the integrated intensities of all iron(II) (blue), iron(III) (green) and iron(IV) (red) complexes under the conditions indicated at the respective ESI-MS spectra A-H. The complexes correspond to [(TPA)Fe^{II}(X)]^{2+/+} (blue), [(TPA)₂Fe₂(O)(TfO)(X)]^{3+/2+} (green), and [(TPA)Fe^{IV}O(X)]^{2+/+} (red). The ligand X is indicated in the top spectra.

measured with 120 AA Baratron (MKS instruments). The zero collision energy was determined by the retarding potential analysis (Figure S2).^[20]

Capillary Flow-Reactor. The flow reactor depicted in Figure 1b and photographed in Figure 8 was made of silica capillaries (internal diameter 100 μm, outer diameter 190 μm, polyimide coating Post-Nova, part no. Z-FSS-100190) and polypropylene mixing-Ts. Mixing-Ts were built by melting polypropylene tubes with a heating gun (we used syringe needle PP covers). The internal shape of the mixing-Ts (pathway from which the solution flows) is given by stainless steel wires with 250 μm diameter positioned to a Y-shape in the plastic tube during the melting procedure (see the photos from the procedure in the Supporting Information). After the plastic cools down, the wires are removed and replaced by silica capillaries. If a leak occurs, the T-piece can be re-melt with the silica capillary inside.

Residence Time Measurements. The residence time of a reaction mixture in the flow reactors was controlled by changing the capillary lengths and/or the N₂ overpressure that regulates the flow rate. The flow rate could be more easily controlled by a syringe pump, if the solutions were placed in syringes. However, we chose to use the N₂ overpressure, because it allows us to work with solutions in vials. The advantage is that the vials with solutions can be rapidly exchanged and the temperature of the solutions can be accurately controlled. Disadvantage is that the flow rate and

Figure 8. The flow-reactors used in the experiments discussed in the paper. a) The flow reactor with 3 mixing-Ts directly connected to the electrospray source (ESI) of the TSQ mass spectrometer. The internal shape of the 3rd mixing-T is highlighted in blue for better visualization. b) The flow-reactor with 1 mixing-T. c) and d) Cooling box in which the flow-reactors are inserted for the monitoring of reactions at low temperatures. The temperature is monitored via the thermometer inserted at the top of the cooling box.

Figure 9. Total ion chromatogram that started to be measured at the moment of placing a vial with $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_2]$ into the flow-reactor. For this measurements, we set the first quadrupole to scan from m/z 190 up to 196 in 0.2 seconds. Left: Residence time measurements for the experiments in Figure 3. Right: Residence time measurements for the experiments in Figure 4.

thereby the residence (reaction) time is difficult to predict and thus must be determined experimentally.

The residence times were determined only in the experiments with one T-piece (experiments shown in Figures 3 and 4). First, both vials were filled with a solvent and the overpressure was regulated to obtain a stable flow. Then, one vial was replaced by a vial with a solution of $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_2]$ and the clock of the ESI-MS experiment was started. The listed residence time is the time difference from the moment of the start of the measurement after the vial exchange and the first appearance of the ion of m/z 193.5 $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{MeCN})]^{2+}$ in the ESI-MS spectrum (see Figure 9). This time also includes the time required for the solution to flow up to the mixing T (prior the mixing of the solutions). Therefore, we keep the connection between the vials and the mixing T as short as possible (much shorter than the capillaries in which the reaction takes place). The residence time measurements were repeated at least 3

times and performed before as well as after the experiments in order to ensure that it kept unchanged.

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